

Privacy and ethical issues of fitness tracking devices: Does it fit your security?

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Abstract: Fitness tracking devices are becoming more popular nowadays. The main feature of these devices is to measure body activity using different sensors and conditions monitors. With an increased number of data breaches in recent years fitness devices are becoming the new target group for attackers since it collects and stores personal health and activity data. The aim of this study is to address the questions related to the collection and use of data from the side of manufacturers and service providers as well as targeting the ignorance of privacy measures of fitness devices usage by the end-users.

Keywords: Privacy, data protection, fitness data, activity monitoring data, wearable devices, fitness trackers, internet of things (IoT)

1 Introduction

Fitness trackers or activity trackers are electronic wearable devices in the group of Internet of Things with sensors and different activity conditions such as steps, calorie consumption, heart rate, blood oxygen level, running and walking speed and distance and more mainly represented in the form of wrist accessories. According to Laricchia (2022), the worldwide shipments of wearable fitness trackers increased 4.5 times within the recent 5 years from 172.7 million units in 2018 to 533.6 million in 2021. With the increasing popularity of wearable devices such as Apple Watch, Fitbit, Garmin, and many others questions related to the ethical use of sensitive information related to the physical state and health of users are

appearing more frequently. These tracking devices are monitoring and collect sensitive personal data about users' lifestyles and habits that can be potentially used by third parties to promote and offer new services and products. Some of the devices are going even beyond that by accessing and analyzing every phone notification from a connected smartphone. One of the main challenges here is the ownership rights of the data collected by fitness trackers and the privacy of personal health data. According to the report of the European Commission (2019), more than 37% of internet users in Europe never read the privacy policy of services they use or subscribe to. Most of the time users are not well informed of the privacy risks of the devices they use every day since it provides helpful information and exciting graphs about activity levels. Additionally, there are almost no actions from the user's side to protect the information collected – in some fitness tracking applications, there is a pre-built with post results on your social network functionality. This study will focus on consequentialism-based ethics and discuss the consequences of ignorance of privacy issues related to the use of fitness and activity-tracking devices.

2 Related Works

With the rise in popularity of fitness trackers and other forms of wearable gadgets, issues about their use are receiving more and more attention. Even though the vast majority of studies are still focused on the accuracy of measures of activity and burned calories and trust in those calculations some studies have looked into concerns connected to the privacy of collecting, processing, encryption, and utilization of data. One of the earliest studies before the boom in popularity of fitness tracking devices conducted by Zhou and Piramuthu (2014) focused on the vulnerabilities in Fitbit trackers – one of the most popular vendors back in 2014. Fitbit itself was not able to provide the privacy of collected data within the communication between the fitness device and the web server. The data from the device's sensors and user's authentication credentials were transferred between the device and web server in clear text format (non-encrypted text) or as plain HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) instructions that can be captured and misused to gain access to connected social networks accounts. Another research conducted in 2017 addressed a similar question of data collection and processing and tested the Man in the middle attack to obtain access to fitness records transmitted from a different fitness device to remote web servers (Fereidooni et al., 2017). This study has shown that regardless of the usage of HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) it was possible to sniff the communication and dump POST requests using another script. Most of the observed fitness

trackers and related mobile applications store data in an unencrypted SQL (Structured Query Language) table. Fereidooni et al. (2017) also observed fitness trackers that do not process data transmission to remote servers, such as Sony Smartband 2 and Oregon Dynamo 2+, even without connection and data transmission to a web server the application stored collected data in plaintext SQL table. This personal data can be accessed and modified by other malicious applications as well as become the target for unscrupulous attackers or companies to get access to other sensitive information such as logins and passwords. With access to passwords and login, malicious actors can try to gain access to other accounts used by the victim since more than 45% of people use the same password for more than two of their accounts on the web (Jocelyn, 2022). Even though there is a risk of data breaches people are continuing to use fitness trackers due to different reasons. Other than modification of data, fitness records can provide sensitive information about the health state of a user. With the lack of technical privacy measures within the connection between fitness devices, phones and web servers companies also can proceed the data to promote or target new products and services based on health data. Although today most IoT fitness devices have a privacy policy where it is described how and for what purpose data might be used many people still do not read or fully understand because they are not aware of their activity data misuse. For sure people are more educated about other personal data, such as social security numbers or passport details and address exposure and misuse, however, health and activity-related data is not yet a part of valuable information worth care. Therefore, here the corresponding questions arise if people understand how their fitness data stored and used or misused and whether there are any consequences related to the ignorance of privacy-related issues in the usage of fitness and activity-tracking devices.

3 Discussion

In this section we will focus on the discussion of the two main research questions related to this research:

Research Question 1: Privacy in processes related to fitness tracking devices data collection, processing and transferring. Is there a place for information security ethics for vendors or it's only a business race?

Research Question 2: Possible consequences of privacy ignorance in fitness tracking devices usage for end-users. What can one lose from another run?

Let's discuss those questions in detail, starting from the data collection, usage, and possible misuse. As it was described above, a major part of fitness devices regardless of vendor and manufacturer on the hardware level uses different sensors and monitors to track activities and movements. Nowadays, almost all fitness trackers require pairing with a smartphone either with the help of Bluetooth or Wi-Fi connection or both for a better exchange of information. Many other related to the topic studies already described the connection between the device and mobile phone to be one of the most vulnerable parts of the network infrastructure of data flow between fitness trackers and smartphones or web servers. One of the studies focused on Fitbit devices targeted the possibility of attacking a device and its network connection to the phone for modification and customization of firmware used (Classen et al., 2018). The attack performed within this study showed that it was possible to gain unauthorized access to the fitness tracker, analyze commands, and send commands such as setting a new alarm and switching off encryption of data. Lack of security within the network infrastructure of a wearable is one of the greatest vulnerabilities existing today within fitness activity tracking devices and wearable technologies (Ching & Singh, 2016). In this study, it was discovered that the main points of intrusion are the network connection between fitness device and mobile phone (over Bluetooth LE), mobile phone to cloud server and backwards (over internet connection). The usage of BLE (or Bluetooth Low Energy) within the connection between the fitness tracking device and smartphone allows for an increase in the battery life of a device from a single charge while the data exchange between two sides of the connection is active most of the time. However, some of the tracking devices use the lowest set of Bluetooth security features available from both sides for connection. Therefore, despite of different security features available for a secure pairing of two devices over Bluetooth connection vendors are the ones who select what is the more important – easier and faster pairing or secure connection. Peker et al. (2022) indicated that different vendors imply different requirements for a secure connection, however, most of them can be violated using brute force attacks. With different versions of this type of connection released by Bluetooth Special Interest Group (SIG), there are different recommendations related to the confidentiality of data, authentication mechanisms and address randomization, however, the implementation of those measures depends on the manufacturer itself. The same applies to the connection between the smartphone and the web server or cloud. Since the connection allows the information flow, gaining access to the fitness

device can lead to unwanted access to user accounts, smartphones, or other types of sensitive user information. Focusing on the fitness trackers themselves, many manufacturers include the feature of contactless payments from the wrist of a user. Examples of those are Garmin Pay, Apple Pay, Fitbit Pay and many other similar technologies. Even though vendors are taking care of bank and card information processed by contactless payment through fitness devices the vulnerability of gaining access through a BLE connection still exists. With access to banking details, attackers can duplicate contactless payment credentials and emulate them through another device. However, does it mean that manufacturers do not care about those vulnerabilities and only think about how their fitness business runs? In some cases, it is not. For instance, some of the vendors apply two types of connection (both BLE and Wi-Fi) between the fitness device and phone also requiring additional authorization by a 4-digit pin. However, to simplify the user experience from the usage of their device they sometimes do not implement limits and validation for brute force attacks. Our smartphones today know that after 3 or 5 times using the wrong pin the phone will be blocked for some time while the same approach is not present on every fitness band or activity tracking device. This is also a measure that should be taken from the side of the manufacturer.

Therefore, the vulnerabilities that might be exploited on a technical level through attacks based on brute force or man-in-the-middle attacks targeting connection over BLE or between devices and the cloud should be managed on the side of the manufacturer. Firmware, encryption of data, validation of user credentials and access attempts, and a secure connection tunnel between smartphone and cloud server are needed for secure data collection, transmission, and processing. These measures are taking additional time and funds for every vendor to address the questions of data privacy and security. Some of the regulations in different regions are covering the essential security measures to be taken from the side of the manufacturer such as the FDA (Food and drug administration), GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act), COPPA (Children's Online Privacy Protection Act). However, some of the above-mentioned regulations are recommended and not all vendors do comply with those or obtain a certificate of approval from them or sometimes even do not obtain any certification. Moreover, the security measures described in the regulations and acts are covering the minimum level of security that should be covered by the manufacturer and most of them do not go above those requirements. Therefore, this brings us back to the case of manufacturers choosing how to secure fitness devices and the connection between them. So here customers have no other option than to rely on the security standards in the company. However, did users ever think

about the consequences of selecting and using fitness tracking devices with poor privacy and security regulations for their data?

The answer to this question is more personal rather than the one related to the culture and beliefs of end-users of fitness trackers. While there is an overall increase in the number of people's concerns related to personal data collection and usage banking details are believed to be the most important for most of the respondents of the GSMA Intelligence survey (Little, 2020). Even though there is an overall tendency for increased concerns related to the use of personal data on different mobile services only a minor part (18%) of respondents finds themselves to be responsible for the data they are sharing with the service providers. For instance, one of the concerns raised in the study of Fietkiewicz and Ilhan (2020) raised the question of whether fitness activity, habits, and even body measurements can be accessed by health insurance companies for decision-making purposes or used against the user of the fitness device. Some of the possible outcomes may include increased cost of health insurance or decline of treatment coverage by the insurance company due to the activity levels of a person. In this study respondents had concerns related to data processing and if third parties can gain access to collected data. Here raises the argument related to data ownership, who is the owner of the collected data, a manufacturer company, an end-user or a third party? One of the most known cases related to data collected from the IoT activity trackers is the case of Hugh Campos (Hinckley, 2017) where the end user had a pacemaker implanted in his body due to medical conditions. Campos experienced the situation when he received a denial of access response to his request to obtain the data collected within 6 months. The collected data here was the property of the company and even though the data was about the end-user the user was not allowed to access or regulate how it should be processed and stored. This case has shown that some of the manufacturers truly believe the data from activity trackers are under the ownership of the company rather than the end user. Another security and privacy concern raises when third-party applications are allowed to gain access to fitness tracking records and measurements. For instance, many fitness tracking devices are supported by Strava - a company that provides tracking and progress analytics features inside of its application. Without the production of own device, the company connects to products from other vendors by the allow permission click from the end user side. However, can a third party be an owner of the collected data and become a victim of a data breach? In 2017 there was a case with this fitness progress-tracking application. With the release of a global heatmap of users by location with more than 3 trillion GPS points located. The questions arose when it was discovered that "Fake Reporter" a cybersecurity company reported the data breach where an anonymous user was using the

application to find and track Israeli soldiers at top-secret military locations (Sitbon, 2022). The app included Segments - roads or trails that have been marked out in advance for use in timed cycling or running competitions by the users of the platform. Users (actual and malicious) were allowed to upload fake segments to the application without even being physically in Israel or any other place of attack. With the notification from the security research team, Strava removed those fake Segments from the system, however the possibility to create fake ones still exists on the platform. Even though the company does not indicate itself as an owner of the data, it is fully responsible for data processing, storage and checking if it can be used for malicious purposes by different actors. However, the philosophy of Strava indicated that users should be the ones responsible for keeping fitness record data safe. Users of the app are allowed to stop sharing their results with the global dashboard as well as their sensitive data. There are a lot of arguments if this measure was helpful for privacy, but if military users educated about security fell for the trap in third-party fitness apps how can a regular user avoid that? The easiest way might be to switch off the GPS tracking and stop using third-party applications. However, this does not guarantee that previously collected data will not be used against the end user. People should take their fitness and health data more seriously since it allows them not only to track their habits but sometimes even stalk their morning jog or cycling. The ownership of collected data should belong to the end-user, however, this end-user should understand how to securely use it for tracking progress, to which third-party applications share the data, understand that violations in privacy may occur and this risk can be mitigated by proper share of data from the user's side.

4 Conclusion

To conclude this study contains arguments about who should be responsible for the implementation of security measures within fitness trackers – manufacturers, end-users, or third-party app developers have the answer – they all. On the side of the manufacturer, there should be security measures indicating not only security through encryption of plain text data but also safe data transfer implemented on the infrastructure level. Authentication mechanisms should include measures against brute force attacks and set limits for maximum trials of wrong pin or password. The third-party app developers should be focused not only on the delegation of data ownership and privacy to the end-user but also consider the implementation of user awareness mechanisms that some of the data might be misused by malicious actors. Service providers need to be transparent about the measures they take to protect the integrity of the data

they gather, and how they manage the flow of information. The end-users of those devices should understand and either accept or mitigate the risks related to the improper usage of their sensitive fitness and activity data while selecting a fitness-tracking device or sharing the data with third-party apps. As the generators or owners of private data end-users should understand that data collected with the help of fitness activity trackers can be accessed and used against them by malicious actors if there are not enough steps are taken in terms of privacy and secrecy. End-users must be aware of the risk they face while using these devices or platforms. Users' familiarity with privacy concerns, as well as their skills and awareness, are crucial to the reliability of the data and information collected by service providers and fitness trackers. As a result, vendors and service providers should start educating users and creating a conducive setting for users to exercise control over their data and privacy by their needs and preferences.

5 References

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